

EVIDENCE OF ZIKA VIRUS CO-EXISTENCE IN SUSPECTED FEBRILE MALARIA AND TYPHOID FEVER PATIENTS IN BENIN CITY, NIGERIA

¹SAIDU JOY ZITGWAI & ²ROBINSON TUEMI DODORU

¹Department of Microbiology, Faculty of Life Sciences, University of Benin, PMB 1154 Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria.

²Institute for Biomedical Research and Innovations, College of Health Sciences, University of Uyo, PMB 1017 Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

Corresponding author: Robinson T. Dodoru, **email:** robinsontuemid@gmail.com

Abstract

Febrile illnesses are the common causes of diseases in the tropics and subtropical countries of the world which often lead to hospital admission. The causative agents are always attributed to malaria and enteric fever, whereby serious consideration of other etiologies of febrile illnesses are not always considered except there is a little or no response to antimalarial and typhoid treatment. This study, therefore, investigates the co-infection of Zika virus, malaria, and typhoid fever in Benin City, Nigeria. A total of 280 blood samples were collected from consented out-patients attending the selected hospitals and serodiagnosis of malaria parasites (MP), typhoid fever and Zika virus (ZIKV) was carried out. Malaria parasites recorded a total positivity of 151 (53.9%) using Microscopy, while typhoid fever recorded a seropositivity of 51 (18.2%) IgM and 9 (3.2%) IgG. ZIKV antibodies was 7 (2.5%) and 41 (14.6%) for IgM and IgG, respectively. A concurrent infection between ZIKV IgG/MP was 31 (11.1%), ZIKV IgG/Typhoid IgG was 2 (0.7%) and ZIKV IgM/Typhoid fever IgM/MP was 3 (8.3%). It was evident that antibodies to Zika virus, coexisting with malaria and typhoid fever is in circulation in the study population. This calls for improved and increased surveillance and the need to make available and strengthened preventive and control measures in order to curtail epidemics.

Keywords: Zika virus, Malaria parasites, Typhoid fever, Serodiagnosis

Introduction

Febrile illnesses are often ascribed to malaria unless confirmed through laboratory testing. Febrile patients regularly exhibit symptoms thought to be caused by malaria or typhoid but are also commonly observed with arbovirus infections (Birhanie *et al.*, 2014). It is a common practice for patients with fever to visit a health-care facility only

if fever persists and after self-medication with two or three different anti-malaria treatments.

Zika virus (ZKV) is among the emerging arboviral diseases that is moving beyond geographical boundaries at a very fast rate. Zika virus, a positive stranded RNA virus was isolated firstly in 1947 in Uganda from jungle rhesus monkey. The first human case was documented in 1952 from residents in the nearby Zika forest region of Uganda with 6.1% of the residents testing positive to specific antibodies to ZKV (Dick *et al.*, 1952; Dick, 1952). The first reported case in Nigeria was by Moore *et al.* (1975), where Zika virus was isolated from three (3) febrile outpatients at the University College Clinic, Ibadan. Zika virus is transmitted through the bite of *Aedes* mosquitoes. Also, cases of transmission through non-vector have been reported - through infected pregnant mother to the fetus (Possas, 2016), blood transfusion and sexual intercourse (Foy *et al.*, 2011; Musso *et al.*, 2014; Musso *et al.*, 2016). Urine, saliva, and breast milk have all been found to contain the virus (Lamb *et al.*, 2016). Infected people are observed to usually get a minor, self-limiting disease from the Zika virus (Lazear and Diamond, 2016; Petersen *et al.*, 2016).

Malaria, on the other hand, is a life threatening disease caused by protozoan of the genus *Plasmodium* that are transmitted through the bites of infected female *Anopheles* mosquitoes. Malaria remains the world's most important tropical parasitic disease with regards to mortality and morbidity (WHO, 2008). It is an important public health disease in both tropical and sub-tropical countries. In Nigeria, malaria is endemic and stable, being a major cause of morbidity and mortality (FMH, 2005).

Typhoid fever, also known as enteric fever, is an acute systemic infection caused by *Salmonella* SPP, a gram-negative bacterium (WHO, 2008). It is largely a disease of developing nations due to their poor standard of hygiene and unavailability of clean water. It is transmitted faeco-orally through contaminated food and water. Transmission by flies such as *Musca domestica* has also been reported (CDC, 2007). Globally, typhoid fever is an important cause of morbidity and mortality in many regions of the world.

Zika virus, malaria and typhoid fever share common symptoms such as sudden fever, headache and joint pain, among others. In most Sub-Saharan countries, including Nigeria, malaria is commonly attributed to all febrile illnesses, whereby serious consideration of other etiologies of febrile illnesses are not always considered except there is little or no response to antimalarial and typhoid treatment. Due to this similarity and lack of specificity of symptoms, misdiagnosis is often common among clinicians. Misdiagnosis is more probable when these infections coexist (Mohammed *et al.*, 2013). Due to lack of vector surveillances or deteriorating vector control, increasing population, mobility and uncontrolled urbanization is leading to the increase in febrile

illnesses causative agents and their coexistence. This research is, therefore, set to investigate the co-infection of Zika virus, malaria and typhoid fever in Benin City, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

This study was carried out in Benin City, the capital of Edo State which is within the south-south of Nigeria on 6° 20' North latitude and 5° 37' East longitude. It is situated approximately 40km north of the Benin River and 320km by road East of Lagos. The City has a humid climate and two (2) climate seasons - the dry and rainy seasons. The dry season lasts from November to March and also a cold humid and dusty harmattan period between December and January. The rainy season is between April and October with average rainfall of 250cm. The average temperature ranges between 22 °C in the rainy season and 28°C in the dry season. The total human population density as at 2015 was 1,200/km²(NPC, 2006).

Ethical Statement

A written statement was collected as an ethical approval from Research and Ethics Committee, Edo State Ministry of Health with reference number HA.577/Vol.11/18/156. Informed consent was obtained from either the participants or their guardians (in the case of minors) prior to the recruitment. Participation was voluntary and the cost of the tests were not borne by the participants.

Sample Collection and Processing

From the two hundred and eighty (280) consented participants, a total of 5ml venous blood was collected from each participant, of which 2ml of each blood sample was decanted in a plain bottle. Half of the blood was used to perform the malaria RDT on site and prepare thick blood films for microscopy. The remaining blood was immediately centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 mins to obtain serum for Zika virus and Typhoid fever screening using the rapid diagnostic kits.

Rapid Diagnostic Testing of Zika Virus

The ZIKVIgG/IgM Rapid Diagnostic Test kits were used to detect the presence of Zika virus antibodies (LUGENE China). It is a chromatographic immunoassay for detecting and distinguishing IgG and IgM antibodies to ZIKV in human blood. In the sample well, one to two drops of serum were introduced, followed by two drops of buffer. After 15 minutes, the results were read. The presence of a colored band/line in the control (C)

area, as well as in the M and/or G band/line, was regarded as positive and accepted for IgM and/or IgG antibodies; whereas the absence of a color band/line in both the G and M band/line, but present in the C band/line, was regarded as negative as described by Kim et al. (2018).

Microscopy and Rapid Test Examination of Malaria Parasites

Microscopy was carried out using thick film. Two drops of anticoagulated blood was placed on a clean glass slide and smeared in a circular motion over an area of about 2cm in diameter. The films were allowed to air-dry at room temperature. The thick films were covered with 3% Giemsa stain for 15 – 30minutes and subsequently washed with clean water and allowed to air dry before observed under the microscope using x100 oil immersion magnification as described by Cheesbrough(2010).

Also, Malaria Ag Pf/Pan Rapid Test Device (Whole Blood) (LUGENE China) was used for malaria diagnosis. The Malaria Ag Pf/Pan antigen rapid test is a qualitative and rapid chromatographic immunoassay for the differential diagnosis of *P. falciparum* histidine rich protein II (P.fHRP-II) and anti-Aldolase antibodies common to *P. falciparum*, *P.malaria*, *P.ovale* and *P.vivax* as described by Achonduh-Atijegbe et al. (2016).

Diagnosis of Typhoid Fever

Diagnosis of typhoid fever was carried out using the Typhoid IgG/IgM Combo rapid test as described by Achonduh-Atijegbe *et al.* (2016). The Typhoid IgG/IgM Combo rapid test cassette is a lateral flow chromatographic immunoassay that can detect and differentiate IgG and IgM antibodies to *S. typhi* and *S. paratyphi* in human blood. A drop of serum was added to the sample well, followed by adding 2 drops of sample diluent. After 10 -15mins, the results were read. The appearance of a colored band in the control (C) line and in the M or G lines was considered as positive for IgM and IgG antibodies, respectively and the absence of a color band in both the G and M lines, but present in the C line, was considered negative.

Data analysis/Results

Data collected from participants were analyzed using SPSS version 20.0 statistical software. Descriptive analysis and proportions were calculated for categorical data and to obtain prevalence. Pearson's logistic regression was employed to examine the association between some factors and tested organisms at 95% confidence intervals (CI). Statistical significance was determined with Chi-square test and the P value was set at 0.05.

A total of 280 consented participants were enrolled in this study. The results showed that malaria parasites, using microscopy and Rapid Diagnostic Test (RDT), had a prevalence of 151(53.9%) and 42(15%), respectively. Seropositivity to Zika virus was 7(2.5%) to IgM and 41(14.6%) to IgG, while typhoid fever recorded a prevalence of 51(18.2%) to IgM and 9(3.2%) to IgG as presented on Figure 1.

Table 1 shows the seroprevalence of malaria parasites, typhoid fever and zika virus based on age in the study population. Age group 0 – 9years did not record any seroprevalence of malaria parasites using RDT, typhoid fever IgM/IgG and Zika virus IgM/IgG. The highest prevalence of malaria parasites using microscopy showed 18.2%, typhoid fever IgM, 6.8%, and Zika virus IgM and IgG was recorded by age group 30-39 years. The signs and symptoms of the study population is presented on table 2. It was observed that out of a total of 280 participants, 127 correspondence reported they had headache, 119 had fever, 73 had chills, 35 had abdominal pains, 5 had diarrhea and 7 reported to the clinic with rashes on their body. Out of a total of 127, 23.3% and 10.7% had malaria parasites using microscopy and RDT, respectively. Correspondence with diarrhea and rash were negative to typhoid fever IgG and Zika virus IgM/IgG.

The female recorded high cases of malaria parasites, typhoid fever IgM/IgG and Zika virus IgM/IgG than their male counterparts as shown on figure 2. The coexistence of zika virus, malaria parasites and typhoid fever was also observed in the study population (Table 3). The co-infection and 95% confidence interval of ZIKV/IgM and Malaria parasites using microscopy is 1.4% (95% CI- 1.95-2.0), ZIKV/MP microscopy is 11.1% (95% CI- 1.73-1.86), ZIKV/Typhoid IgM is 1.1% (95% CI- 1.87-2.01) and ZIKV/Typhoid IgG is 0.7% (95% CI- 1.44-2.12).

Figure 1: Prevalence of Zika Virus, Malaria Parasites and Typhoid Fever in the Study Population.

Key: MP-malaria parasites, RDT - Rapid diagnostic test, ZIKV -Zika virus, IgM - Immunoglobulin M, IgG-Immunoglobulin G

Table 1: Seroprevalence of Malaria Parasites, Typhoid Fever and Zika Virus based on Age Distribution in the Study Population.

Variables	Malaria Parasite		Typhoid fever		Zika virus	
	Microscopy	RDT	IgM	IgG	IgM	IgG
0-9	3(1.1%)	-	-	-	-	-
10-19	13(4.6%)	10(3.6%)	4(1.4%)	-	1(0.4%)	2(0.7%)
20-29	37(13.2%)	9(3.2%)	9(3.2%)	1(0.4%)	2(0.7%)	7(2.5%)
30-39	51(18.2%)	8(2.9%)	19(6.8%)	3(1.1%)	2(0.7%)	13(4.6%)
40-49	18(6.4%)	6(2.1%)	5(1.8%)	1(0.4%)	2(0.7%)	6(2.1%)
>50	29(10.4%)	9(3.2%)	14(5.0%)	4(1.4%)	-	13(4.6%)
Total	151(53.9%)	42(15%)	51(18.2%)	9(3.2%)	7(2.5%)	41(14.6%)

Key: RDT- Rapid diagnostic test, IgM- Immunoglobulin M, IgG-Immunoglobulin G

Table 2: Signs and Symptoms of the Study Population

Variables	N=280	Malaria Parasite		Typhoid fever		Zika virus	
		Microscopy	RDT	IgM	IgG	IgM	IgG
Headache	127	82(23.3%)	30(10.7%)	21(7.5%)	3(1.1%)	5(1.8%)	20(7.1%)
Fever	119	73(26.1%)	26(9.3%)	23(8.2%)	6(2.1%)	2(0.7%)	20(7.1%)
Chill	73	39(13.9%)	15(5.4%)	13(4.6%)	3(1.1%)	1(0.4%)	7(2.5%)
Abdominal discomfort	35	16(5.7%)	6(2.1%)	6(2.1%)	2(0.7%)	-	4(1.4%)
Diarrhoea	5	1(0.4%)	1(0.4%)	2(0.7%)	-	-	-
Rash	7	2(0.7%)	1(0.4%)	1(0.4%)	-	-	-

Key: N- Number, RDT- Rapid diagnostic test, IgM - Immunoglobulin M, IgG-Immunoglobulin G

Figure 2: Seropositivity of Malaria Parasites, Typhoid fever and Zika Virus based on Gender in the Study Population.

Table 3: Co-existence of Zika Virus, Malaria Parasites and Typhoid Fever.
Key: MP- malaria parasites, RDT- Rapid diagnostic test, ZIKV- Zika virus, IgM- Immunoglobulin M, IgG-Immunoglobulin G

Disease test	Number positive	%(95% CI)
MP microscopy	151	53.9(1.40-1.52)
MP RDT	42	15(1.85-1.89)
MP microscopy/MP RDT	41	14.6(1.07-0.98)
ZIKVIgM	7	2.5(1.96-1.99)
ZIKVIgG	41	14.6(1.81-1.90)
ZIKVIgM and ZIKVIgG	3	1.1(1.84-2.01)
Typhoid IgM	51	18.2(1.77-1.86)
Typhoid IgG	9	3.2(1.95-1.99)
Typhoid IgM and Typhoid IgG	9	3.2(1.80-1.89)
Co-infection with Zika virus		
ZIKVIgM/MP microscopy	4	1.4(1.95-2.0)
ZIKVIgG/MP microscopy	31	11.1(1.73-1.86)
ZIKVIgM/MP RDT	1	0.4(1.51-2.21)
ZIKVIgG/MP RDT	7	2.5(1.71-1.95)
ZIKVIgM/Typhoid IgM	3	1.1(1.87-2.01)
ZIKVIgG/Typhoid IgG	2	0.7(1.44-2.12)
ZIKVIgM/Typhoid IgM/MP microscopy	3	1.1(1.87-2.01)
ZIKVIgG/Typhoid IgG/MP microscopy	2	0.7(1.44-2.12)

Key: MP-malaria parasites, RDT- Rapid diagnostic test, ZIKV-Zika virus, IgM-immunoglobulin M, IgG-Immunoglobulin G, CI-confidence interval, 95% CIs based on likelihood method.

Discussion

This study reports the sero-coinfection of Zika virus, malaria parasites, and typhoid fever in Benin City, Nigeria. Zika virus, malaria parasites, and *Salmonellaspp* are febrile-causing pathogens and a major public health burden in tropical and subtropical countries. In recent times, it is common to find patients receiving malaria and typhoid treatment as the major or the only cause of febrile illness.

Zika virus is one of the *flaviviruses* associated with febrile sicknesses in the

tropics and sub-tropical regions of the world. The use of rapid diagnostic test kit has the benefit of being able to identify nonstructural 1 (NS1) antigen as well as differential IgM/IgG antibodies to ZIKV, and other viruses in human blood. IgM can be detected 3 to 5 days after the commencement of disease in primary infection and 1 to 2 days after the onset of sickness in secondary dengue infections; it can last up to 3 months while IgG develops within days after IgM and last for a life-time (Gubler, 1996). In this study, Zika virus showed a seroprevalence of 7(2.5%) and 41(14.6%) to IgM and IgGRDTs, respectively. This is not in agreement with the work of Out *et al.* (2020), where they reported 10% to IgM and 12% to IgG of ZIKV in Cross River State. The variation in the prevalence rate could be associated with differences in the sample size, study location and period of sample collection.

The overall prevalence of malaria was 151(53.9%) using microscopy, and 42(15%) using the Rapid Diagnostic Test (RDT). The prevalence of 53.9% using microscopic method is higher than 40.5% in South Eastern Nigeria (Uneke *et al.*, 2006), 43.1% reported in Rivers (Wogu and Nduka, 2018), 43.4% in Cameroon (Achonduh-Atijegbe *et al.*, 2016), and higher than 27% reported by Abdulahi *et al.* (2009); but lower than 85.7% in Enugu (Ayogu *et al.*, 2016), 71.4% in Cross River (Udoh *et al.*, 2013); lower than that of Aribodor *et al.* (2003) and Onyido *et al.* (2010) who reported 76% and 62% prevalence in Azia and Umudioka communities in Anambra State.

The disparity in prevalence could be related to changes in sample size and sampling procedures, environmental parameters such as the research area's temperature and humidity. The prevalence of 42(15%) using malaria RDT is seen to be higher than 35.6% reported in Kaduna (Idoko *et al.*, 2014) and 21.6% from under-five children in Ibadan (Adebisi *et al.*, 2018), but lower than 56.8% from age 6 (months) to 15years in Cameroon (Achonduh-Atijegbe *et al.*, 2016). Also, variation could be attributed to government malaria intervention programme or distribution and use of Long Lasting Insecticidal Treated Nets (LLINs). These LLINs are known to reduce malaria cases by 50% and decrease mortality in children by 15-30% where coverage rates are high (Aribodor *et al.* 2011).

The comparison of malaria RDT to microscopic method in the diagnosis of malaria parasites status in this research showed no significant difference between the two methods in the determination of malaria status. However, microscopy performed better than the rapid diagnostic test kit. Microscopy, using Giemsa method, is regarded as the most suitable and gold standard for malaria diagnosis because it is inexpensive to perform, able to differentiate malaria species and even quantify malaria parasites. In the age of high-quality light emitting diodes (LED), illumination and solar battery chargers, microscopy has become more feasible in remote areas (Wongsrichanalari *et al.*, 2007).

Typhoid fever is a serious public health problem. It causes severe systemic

infection in lesser developed areas of the world. It is a systemic, mortal and contagious disease caused by *Salmonella* spp. This bacterium specifically affects humans in a highly-adapted manner. It is found more habitually in underdeveloped countries where overload of population and improper sanitation are common (Mitra et al., 2010).

Conclusion

In this study, we made use of the Rapid Diagnostic Test kits, which is known to offer simplicity, speed, economy and early diagnosis with high sensitivity and specificity. The detection of IgM antibodies suggests acute typhoid in the early phase of infection, while the detection of both IgG and IgM antibodies suggests acute typhoid in the middle phase of infection. Since IgG antibodies can persist for more than 2 years after typhoid infection, the detection of specific IgG antibodies cannot differentiate between acute and convalescent cases (Olopoenia and King, 2000). Therefore, it was observed that typhoid fever recorded seropositivity of 51(18.2%) for IgM and 9(3.2%) for IgG. This is seen to be higher than 16 (26.66%) for IgM and 3 (5%) for IgG as reported by Qudisia et al. (2020). A combined seroprevalence of typhoid fever antibodies was 21.4%, which is seen to be low than 26% (Garg, 2017), 42.6% (Jahan et al., 2021), 48% (Mehta et al., 2017), and 70% (Sharanya et al., 2016).

The occurrence of ZIKV, malaria parasites and typhoid fever in relation to symptoms showed seropositivity. People who have headache, fever, chills, diarrhoea or rash and have a proportion occurrence of both ZIKV, malaria parasites and typhoid fever are more likely to have the infection than those who do not. Several investigations have reported similar clinical symptoms (Shahin *et al.*, 2009; 2012; Sow *et al.*, 2016; Mohamed et al., 2023). This is extremely important for public health since patients who come with these symptoms at clinics and hospitals are likely to be treated for malaria and/or typhoid fever, particularly in malaria-endemic countries like Nigeria.

Concurrent infection with two or more different pathogens often leads to an overlap of their clinical features that can lead to missed diagnostic challenge to the physician, especially in endemic areas (Epelboin *et al.*, 2012). Research has shown the concurrent infection of mosquito-borne pathogens and others is highly possible. There have been reports of concurrent infection of Zika virus (Chaves *et al.*, 2018; Estofolete *et al.*, 2019), Chikungunya and Zika virus (Villamil-Gomez *et al.*, 2016). Out of the 280 study population, ZIKV, Malaria parasites and Typhoid fever were co-existing together. A total of 1.4%, 11.1% and 1.1% had concurrent ZIKVIgM/MP, ZIKVIgG/MP and ZIKVIgM/Typhoid fever IgM, respectively. Concurrent infection of ZIKV and malaria parasites have been reported (Sow *et al.*, 2016; Out *et al.*, 2020). Research has shown that the co-existence of arboviruses with malaria may result in more severe clinical

manifestations, particularly thrombocytopaenia and anaemia (Epelboin *et al.*, 2012). Nigeria is one of the few African countries that limit investigation of febrile illnesses to malaria and typhoid with complete neglect to other febrile pathogens such as viral infections. Generally, viral infections suppress the natural immunity of the host and this often allows opportunistic infections to set in (Dawurung *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, a concurrent infection of ZIKV, malaria and typhoid fever as observed in this study, is a pointer to the fact that co-infections are in existence.

References

- Abdulahi, K., Abubakar, U., Adamu, T., Daneji, A.I., Aliyu, R.U., Jiya, N., Ibraheem, M.T.O., Nata'ala, S.U. (2009). Malaria in Sokoto, North-western Nigeria. *African Journal of Biotechnology* 8, 7101-7105.
- Achonduh-Atijegbe, O.A., Mfuh, K.O., Mbange, A.H.E., Chedjou, J.P., Taylor, D.W., Nerurkar, V.R., Mbacham, W.F., Leke, R (2016). Prevalence of malaria, typhoid, toxoplasmosis and rubella among febrile children in Cameroon. *BMC Infectious Diseases* 16, 1-9.
- Adebisi, N.A., Dada-Adegbola, H.O., Dairo, M.D., Ajayi, I.O., Ajumobi, O.O.(2018). Performance of malaria rapid diagnostic test in febrile under-five children at Oni Memorial Children's Hospital in Ibadan, Nigeria, 2016. *Pan African Medical Journal* 30, 1-8.
- Aribodor, D.N., Njoku, O.O., Eneanya, C.I., Onyali, I.O. (2003). Studies on the prevalence of malaria and management practices of Azia community, Ihiala L.G.A, Anambra State, Nigeria. *Nigeria Journal of Parasitology* 24, 33-38.
- Ayogu, E.E., Ukwe, C.C., Nna, E.O. (2016). Assessing the reliability of microscopy and rapid diagnostic tests in malaria diagnosis in areas with varying parasite density among older children and adult patients in Nigeria. *Journal of Postgraduate Medicine* 62, 150–156.
- Birhanie, M., Tessema, B., Ferede, G., Endris, M. and Enawgaw, B. (2014). Malaria, Typhoid Fever, and Their Coinfection among Febrile Patients at a Rural Health Center in Northwest Ethiopia: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Advance in Medicine* 10, 1-8

- CDC-Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (2007). Malaria: Life cycle of Plasmodium species. [http://www.cdcgov/malaria/plasmodium species.html/](http://www.cdcgov/malaria/plasmodium%20species.html/) Accessed on 1-5-2012.
- Chaves, B.A., Orfano, A.S., Nogueira, P.M., Rodrigues, N.B., Campolina, T.B., Nacif-Pimenta, R., Pires, A.C.A.M., Vieira Júnior, A.B., da Costa Paz, A., da Costa Vaz, E.B., Guerra, M.G.B., Silva, B.M., de Melo, F.F., Norris, D.E., de Lacerda, M.V.G., Pimenta, P.F.P., Secundino, N.F.C. (2018). Coinfection with Zika Virus (ZIKV) and Dengue Virus Results in Preferential ZIKV Transmission by Vector Bite to Vertebrate Host the Journal of Infectious Diseases 218, 563–571
- Cheesbrough, M. (2010). Test for Malaria Parasites. District Laboratory Practice in Tropical Countries (2nd ed, part 1). Cambridge University Press, New York, pp 239-258.
- Dick, G.W. (1952). Zika virus pathogenicity and physical properties. Transactions of the Royal Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene 46, 521–534.
- Dick, G.W., Kitchen, S.F., Haddow, A.J. (1952). Zika virus. Isolations and serological specificity. Transactions of the Royal Society Tropical Medicine and Hygiene 46, 509–520.
- Epelboin, L., Hanf, M., Dussart, P., Ouar-Epelboin, S., Djossou, F., Nacher, M., Carme, B. (2012). Is dengue and malaria co-infection more severe than single infections? A retrospective matched-pair study in French Guiana. *Malaria Journal* 11, 1-8.
- Estofolete, C.F., Terzian, A.C.B., Colombo, T.E., Guimarães, G.F., Ferraz, H.C.J., da Silva, R.A., Greque, G.V., Nogueira, M.L. (2019). Co-infection between Zika and different Dengue serotypes during DENV outbreak in Brazil. *Journal of Infection and Public Health* 12, 178–181
- FMH-Federal Ministry of Health (2005). National Treatment Guidelines. A publication of the Federal Ministry of Health, Abuja, Nigeria: p.47.

- Foy, B.D., Kobylinski, K.C., Chilson, J.L., Blitvich, B.J., Travassos da Rosa, A., Haddow, A.D., Lanciotti, R.S., Tesh, R.B. (2011). Probable non-vectorborne transmission of Zika virus, Colorado, USA. *Emerging Infectious Diseases* 17, 880–882.
- Garg, N.A. (2017). Comparative study of Widal test and Typhidot in rapid diagnosis of Typhoid fever. *Int J Med Res Prof* 3, 88-92.
- Gubler, D.J., 1996. Serological diagnosis of dengue haemorrhagic fever. *Dengue Bull* 20, 20–23.
- Idoko, M.O., Ado, S.A., Umoh, V.J. (2014). Serological survey of dengue virus immunoglobulin M among febrile patients in kaduna metropolis, Nigeria. *Aceh International Journal of Science and Technology* 3, 152–158.
- Jahan, N., Khatoon, R., Mishra, P., Mehrotra, S., Ahmad, S. (2021). A comparative evaluation of rapid card and widal slide agglutination tests for rapid diagnosis of typhoid fever. *Med J DY Patil Vidyapeeth* 14, 409-414.
- Kim, Y.H., Lee, J., Ki, Y.E., Chong, C.K., Pinchemel, Y., Reisdorfer, F., Coelho, J.B., Dias, R.F., Bae, P.K., Gusmao, Z.P.M., Ahn, H.J., Nam, H.W. (2018). Development of a Rapid Diagnostic Test Kit to Detect IgG/IgM Antibody to Zika virus using Monoclonal Antibodies to the envelope and Non-structural Protein 1 of the virus. *Korean Journal of Parasitology* 59, 61-70.
- Lamb, L.E., Bartolone, S.N., Kutluay, S.B., Robledo, D., Porras, A., Plata, M., Chancellor, M.B., (2016). Advantage of urine based molecular diagnosis of Zika virus. *International Urology and Nephrology* 16, 1406-1409.
- Lazear, H.M., Diamond, M.S. (2016). Zika virus: new clinical syndromes and its emergence in the Western Hemisphere. *Journal of Virology* 90, 4864–4875.
- Mehta, A., Sharma, D., Singh, V.P. (2017). Comparative evaluation of diagnostic performance of Blood culture, Lateral flow immunoassay, Tube Widal and Slide Widal test in diagnosis of Enteric fever using a Composite Reference Standard. *J Med Sci Clin Res* 5, 27963-27971.

- Mitra, R., Kumar, N. (2010). Trigunayat A, Bhan S. New advances in the rapid diagnosis of typhoid fever. *African Journal of Microbiology Resource* 4, 1747-1753.
- Mohamed, A.A., Ebeid, B.A.M., Abdellatif, A.A.R., Malak, M. (2023). Use of onsite typhoid IgG/IgM combo test as rapid diagnostic test for typhoid fever Beni-Suef University *Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences* 12, 1-5.
- Mohammed, A., Syed, F., Omrana, P., Syed, I., Mubarak, M., Mutasim, M. (2013). Dengue fever in a border state between Sudan and Republic of South Sudan: epidemiological perspectives. *Journal of Public Health and Epidemiology* 5, 319—24.
- Moore, D.L., Causey, O.R., Carey, D.E., Reddy, S., Cooke, A.R., Akinkugbe, F.M. (1975). Arthropod-borne viral infection of man in Nigeria, 1964–1970. *Annals of Tropical Medicine and Parasitology* 69, 49–64.
- Musso, D., Gubler, D.J. (2016). Zika virus. *Clinical Microbiology Review* 29, 487–524.
- Musso, D., Nhan, T., Robin, E., Roche, C., Bierlaire, D., Zisou, K., Shan Yan, A., Cao-Lormeau, V.M., Broult, J.(2014). Potential for Zika virus transmission through blood transfusion demonstrated during an outbreak in French Polynesia, November 2013 to February 2014. *Euro Surveillance* 19, 20761.
- National Population Commission (NPC). (2006). A publication of the Population Census of Nigeria.
- Olopoenia, L., King, A. (2000). Widal agglutination test – 100 years later: Still plagued by controversy. *Postgraduate Medical Journal* 76, 80-84.
- Onyido, A.E., Agbata, V.O., Umeanaeto, P.U., Obiukwu, M.O. (2011). Ecology of malaria vectors in a rainforest sub urban community of Nigeria. *African Research Review* 5, 293-105.
- Otu, A.A., Udoh, U.A., Ita, O.I., Hicks, J.P., Egbe, W.O. and Walley, J. (2020). A cross-sectional survey on the seroprevalence of dengue fever in febrile patients attending health facilities in Cross River State, Nigeria. *PLoS ONE* 14(4):1-12

- Petersen, L.R., Jamieson, D.J., Powers, A.M., Honein, A.M., Honein, M.A. (2016). Zika virus. *New England Journal of Medicine* 374, 1552–1563.
- Possas, C. (2016). Zika: what we do and do not know based on the experiences of Brazil. *Epidemiology and Health* 38, 1-7.
- Qudsia, F., Rehan, M., Riaz, S. (2020). Molecular analysis of immunoglobulins related to salmonella typhi in pediatric patients. *Arch Pathol Clin Res.* 4, 005-010. DOI: 10.29328/journal.apcr.1001017.
- Sharanya, K., Vinod, K., Lakshmi, K. (2016). Comparison of Widal and typhoid Immunoglobulin M and Immunoglobulin G in rapid and early diagnosis of enteric fever. *Asian J Pharma Clin Res* 9, 243-246.
- Sow, A., Loucoubar, C., Diallo, D., Faye, O., Ndiaye, Y., Senghor, C.S., Dia, A.T., Faye, O., Weaver, S.C., Diallo, M., Malvy, D., Alpha, A. (2016). Concurrent malaria and arbovirus infections in Kedougou, southeastern Senegal. *Malaria Journal* 15, 1-7.
- Udoh, E.E., Oyo-Ita, A.E., Odey, F.A., Eyong, K.I., Oringanje, C.M., Oduwole, O.A., Okebe, J.U., Esu, E.B., Meremikwu, M.M. (2013). Malarimetric indices among Nigerian children in a rural setting. *Malaria Research and Treatment* 4, 1-4.
- Uneke, C.J., Ogbu, O., Nwojiji, V. (2006). Potential risk of induced malaria by blood transfusion in South-eastern Nigeria. *McGill Journal of Medicine* 9, 8–13.
- Villamil-Go´mez, W.E., Rodri´guez-Morales, A.J., Uribe-Garcia, A.M., Gonza´lez-Arismendy, E., Castellanos, J.E., Calvo, E.P., Alvarez-Mon, M., Musso, D. (2016). Zika, dengue, and chikungunya co-infection in a pregnant woman from Colombia. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases* 51, 135–138.
- WHO-World Health Organization (2008). Economic cost of malaria. Roll back malaria program report. <http://who.malariaroll-backmalaria/> accessed on 1-5-2012.
- Wogu, M.N., Nduka, F.O. (2018). Evaluating Malaria Prevalence Using Clinical Diagnosis Compared with Microscopy and Rapid Diagnostic Tests in a Tertiary Healthcare Facility in Rivers State, Nigeria. *Journal of Tropical Medicine*

Wongsrichanalai, C., Barcus, M.J., Muth, S., Sutamihardja, A., Wernsdorfer, W.H. (2007). A Review of Malaria Diagnostic Tools: Microscopy and Rapid Diagnostic Test (RDT). *American Society of Tropical Medicine and Hygiene* 77, 119–127.